

THE IMPACT OF AMIR TEMUR'S STATEHOOD EXPERIENCE ON THE FORMATION OF CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the impact of Amir Temur's statehood experience on the formation of civil society institutions from a historical-philosophical perspective. In particular, it reveals the importance of the principles of justice, rule of law, social balance, and economic stability in public administration. It also highlights the historical model of relations between the state and society based on the Temur Tuzuklari.

KEYWORDS

statehood civil society justice rule of law
governance social balance Sahibqiron
consultation

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